

METHODOLOGY FOR THE STUDY OF COMPUTER TERMS

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Annotation: The article deals with the systemic features of English and Russian computer terminology. The interest to this issue is motivated by the fact that the terms are not stable, and the lexical and semantic processes are constantly developing due to new computer and information technologies. Some processes are regarded here.

В данной статье рассматривается системное функционирование компьютерной терминологии английского языка. Отражены виды интерференции и ее причины, неоднородность средств терминологической номинации, а также лексико-семантические процессы и явления, характерные для данной терминологии.

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi kompyuter terminologiyasining tizimli ishlashi muhokama qilinadi. Interferensiya turlari va uning sabablari, terminologik nominatsiya vositalarining bir xilligi, shuningdek, ushbu terminologiyaga xos bo'lgan leksik-semantik jarayonlar va hodisalar o'z aksini topgan.

. **Keywords:** *computer terminology; systemic features; system of terms; lexical; semantic processes.*

In modern society, the dynamic development of information and computer technology leads to the corresponding development of thermal technologies in this area. The continuous penetration of computer projects, concepts, terms in everyday life is dictated by the need studying terminology from a linguistic point of view. Scientists already managed to study some processes, but the characteristic mobility of the mines are increasingly of interest for further research. Today there are several thousand terminologies, each of which which functions as a system and is formed on the basis of natural language. The constituent elements of the terminological system are lexical units of the language are used for special purposes, i.e., a term. Modern researchers in their scientific works describe many definitions of the terminological system and its functioning in the language environment. First of all, when studying certain processes, one should consider the main linguistic patterns to which the lexical as in the formation of the terminological field.

As noted above, the terminology of the computer sphere is constantly obviously replenished due to progressive improvements in technology and technology. And this, from the point of view of linguistics, can explain the inter-linguistic interference, which manifests itself in the form of assimilation of mutual terms in the recipient language, as well as in the adaptation of terminological logical units by tracing, e.g. monitor 'monitor', Internet 'Internet', computer 'computer', browser 'browser', etc. Clarified terms are easier to "settle" in the system of the receiving language, since there is no formal adaptation in the process. You can also meet different types of tracing-phrases that convey word translation of borrowed words. For example, computer engineer 'computer engineer', binary code 'binary code. But at this stage, there are signs of synonymy, as a result of which terms of other origin may be superseded. Interlingual interference is closely related to intralinguistic interference, since in the process of integrating computer terminological units into mutual existing language is the transfer of accumulated knowledge from the language - source into the recipient language. The presence of interdisciplinary communications thorny area with subjects such as mathematics, radio electronics, computer technology, sometimes even economics, testifies to the mathematical interference. For example, the meaning of the term to convert 'convert' coincides with an economic concept. Exploring computer terms and their origin, one can state that in the Russian language there are many terms that have Chinese, French and English base, e.g. processor, comparator, interface. The reasons for the possibility of such borrowings are there is a lack of similar concepts or words in the receiving language howling environment. When considering the etymology of this layer of vocabulary, There are cases of internationalization of computer terms: smart map, service provider, client-server, CD. Such words to sufficiently transparent etymologically in structure, and in different linguistic systems, the external form and meaning of the concept practically coincide. Computer terminology, as opposed to conventional lexical units, has characteristic features that are not inherent in natural language, which is how they differ from the common language context. If an ordinary literary word belongs to the principle stability, then the computer term is based on the principle of arbitrariness. It is this uniqueness that is the reason for justifying the fact that the terminology of the computer field is more common richer and richer than the language units of that language, to the system of which it adapts to include elements that are not part of the general vocabulary. For example, outside the Russian language there are such terms as driver, cartridge, because their structures are morphological and nological levels are not typical for the Russian language.

In modern writing, a combination of Russian and English bases is widely used words, which is also a feature of computer terms: URL- address, IT company, smart card,

SIM card, Web page, USB port. Terminology is a subsystem of the general lexico-semantic system we are a language that contains all structural types of words, all semantical processes inherent in vocabulary as a whole formation of terminological units can be traced in the process of peace. V. M. Leichik notes that "in every terminological the system includes basic (simple) derivatives and complex terms, and also a number of terms of the basic branches of knowledge, attracting terms (from related sciences) and general scientific (general technical) terms without which it is impossible to construct terms this sphere". Analyzing text corpora, the following types of terms: single-component and multi-component, words and phrases of a specialized orientation, for example, data, loading, desktop computer. You can also meet special the former form, when the term includes symbols in the form of numbers, graphical characters, letters: 3D printer. The Russian language is dominated by one-word computer terms, while in English more complex phrases. Computer terminology is characterized by semantic blurring, which is confirmed by synonymy and antonymy, polysemy and homonymy. Thus, it can be noted that in the sublanguage of this area the same lexico-semantic phenomena occur as in natural language. Synonymy used in computer terminology, defines several examples of the term that refer to the same to the same fragment of use, but complements the concept, detailed and differentiating it, for example, in English: hack, crash, crack, break in 'crack something'; in Russian: start, start, start, turn on, load means to start something. Depending on from the mode of action of the form of the term can be modified: processing ka - processing. There are also so-called semantic doublets, where the old term is used in parallel with the new: erase - hard drive. This method of forming synonymy, when a series includes several concepts that are close in meaning, confirms the mobility of computer terms within the system.

In the terminology of the computer field, antonymy is represented as the name of concepts that have the opposite meaning: save - delete 'save - delete'; paste - cut 'insert - cut'; install-remove 'install - remove'. Terms-antonyms of this area in Russian. In English, they have prefixes a-, anti-, bez- / bes-, or de-: synchronous - asynchronous, virus - antivirus, wired - wireless, constructive torus - destructor; in English a-, anti-, de-, -less: encode - decode, virus - antivirus, bug - debug, wire - wireless. Often English antonym terms can be formed using prepositions, for example, log in - log off 'log in - log out'. The semantic phenomenon of polysemy also takes place in computer thorn terminology. In the process of changing or expanding, and sometimes narrowing of the original meaning of a certain term is formed polysemy, i.e., the appearance of several meanings in a given term, associated known to each other. In Russian, if we consider the word tire, as a computer term, it has the following meaning: path or a channel electrically connected to one or more conductors, data transfer. In a non-terminological sense, a tire has meanings:

- 1) a hoop mounted on the rim of transport vehicles;

- 2) a nationality with a total number of 120 thousand people living on territories of India;
- 3) medical device for injuries and diseases of bones, joints, soft tissues, etc.

Homonym terms are somewhat different from natural homonyms. language. In computer terminology, the most common inter- industry homonyms, terms that can be used in several different terminological spheres, but at the same time have different meanings. For example, in the Big Dictionary of Foreign Words (2007), topology is “a part of geometry that studies the qualitative properties of figures (i.e., does not depending on concepts such as length, angles, straightness and etc.” In another dictionary, topology is the physical or logical distribution of network nodes...”. Many researchers admit that due to the variability of the meaning of the polysemic term, these words acquire homonymy.

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